

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 3

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№3 (2022) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2022-3>

Бош муҳаррир:

Холбеков Муҳаммаджон

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Тўхтасинов Илҳом

ф.ф.д., доцент (Ўзбекистон)

Главный редактор:

Холбеков Муҳаммаджон

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Тухтасинов Илҳом

к.ф.н., доцент (Ўзбекистон)

Editor in Chief:

Kholbekov Muhammadjan

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

Tuhtasinov Ilhom

Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Uzbekistan)

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр

академик (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўгли

ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова

ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким

ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил

ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед

к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт

Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Ҳамидулла

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддиқова Ирода

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар

ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек

масбул котиб, доцент (Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр

академик (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умар оглы

д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова

д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бокиева Гуландом

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким

д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил

д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед

к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Джеймс Форт

Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Балтабоев Ҳамидулла

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддиқова Ирода

д.ф.н., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар

д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Юсупов Ойбек

отв. секретарь, доцент (Ўзбекистон)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov

academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed

Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort

University of Michigan (USA)

Umarkhodjaev Mukhtar

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda

Doc. of philol. sci., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar

Doc. of philol. sci. (Georgia)

Yusupov Oybek

Ass. prof. (Uzbekistan) - Senior Secretary

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Sharipov S.S. ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЯ (ТАРЖИМА ЛЕКСИКОГРАФИЯСИ) РИВОЖЛАНИШИНИНГ АСОСИЙ ЖИҲАТЛАРИ.....	5
2. Akhadova Guzal Imatulloevna, Mavlyanova Nilufar Suvankulovna METHODOLOGY AND PRINCIPLES OF USING ROLE PLAYING IN FOREIGN LESSONS.....	12
3. Atayeva Khusniya Kurashevna, Fayziyeva Yulduz Yusupovna USING INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES AND TEACHING METHODS AT THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE LESSON.....	17
4. Absamatova Gulhayo Bakhodirovna LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF SIGN LANGUAGE AUTOMATIZATION.....	24
5. Shuhratova Visola jamshid qizi KAZUO ISHIGURONING "DAFN ETILGAN GIGANT"ASARIDAGI KONSEPTLAR UYG'UNLIGI.....	30
6. Bazarova Shahlo Shuxratovna KOREYS ADIBASI SHIN KYON SUK IJODINING O'ZIGA XOSLIGI XUSUSIDA.....	36
7. Kasimova Adiba Nasirovna TRANSLATION METHODS AND TECHNIQUES OF PUBLICISTIC MATERIALS.....	41
8. Арзикулова Хуршида Акабаралиевна “ГОРАЦИЙ” ТРАГЕДИЯСИДА ИНСОНИЙ ФАЗИЛАТЛАР ВА ОИЛАВИЙ БУРЧ.....	47
9. Mamadjanova Nargiza Mahmudjanovna ZAMONAVIY INGLIZ TILIDA MUROJAATNING KOMMUNIKATIV FUNKSIYASI.....	52
10. Икромова Нигина ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ТЕКСТА (НА ПРИМЕРЕ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННОГО ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯ Ч.АЙТМАТОВА “ПРОЩАЙ, ГУЛЬСАРИ!”).....	58
11. Абдусаматов Зафарбек Нурмат ўғли ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИДА АНТРОПОНИМЛАР ТУРИ ВА ИФОДА ШАКЛЛАРИ.....	65
12. Abduraxmonova Nilufar Zaynobbiddin qizi, Vosiljonov Azizbek Boxodirjon o'g'li O'ZBEK TILI ELEKTRON KORPUSIDA DIALEKTAL KORPUS YARATISHNING NAZARIY MASALALARI.....	70
13. Achilova Noila Hamroqulovna SUYUQLIK MIQDORINI ANGLATUVCHI LISONIY BIRLIKLARNING PRAGMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	75
14. Tadjibayeva Gulzoda ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKDA ANTROPOTSENTRIK PARADIGMA.....	81
15. Begimqulova Dilobar INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA REDUPLIKATIVLIKNING MORFOLOGIK IFODALANISHINING QIYOSIY TAHLILI.....	86
16. Amonova Zilola Qodirovna, Axrorova Zufnunabegim Rizvonovna HUSAYNIYNING BADIY MAHORATI.....	93

17. Наргиза Жахонова ТАВТОЛОГИЯ ВА ПЛЕОНАЗМНИНГ ЎРГАНИЛИШ ТАРИХИГА БИР НАЗАР.....	99
18. O`dayeva Shahnoza Shuxratovna</b> RANG, MAZA-TA`M MA`NOSINI ANGLATUVCHI LISONIY BIRLIKLARNING PRAGMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI.....	105
19. Gaybullayeva Malokhat Pulatovna HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF ENGLISH DIALECTS.....	111
20. Xamrayeva Zebiniso Xaydar qizi QO`SHMA GAPNING STRUKTUR – SEMANTIK TAHLILI (INGLIZ TILI ASOSIDA).....	116
21. Umaraliev Dildora Takhirjanovna PECULIARITIES OF LEGAL TERMS.....	122
22. Дилноза Раматжановна Рузматова ХОЛИД ҲОСИЙНИЙ АСАРЛАРИДА АФҒОНИСТОН ПЕРСПЕКТИВАСИ: ТАРИХИЙ ВА БАДИИЙ ТАЛҚИН.....	128
23. Sodiqova Yulduz Furqatovna LITERARY TEXT AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUISTIC RESEARCH AND THE PROBLEM OF ITS INTERPRETATION.....	134
24. Bozorbekov A. LOGISTIKA TERMINOLOGIYA TIZIMINING XUSUSIYATLARI.....	138
25. Ulikova Mavluda CRITERIA FOR THE SELECTION OF TERMS DENOTING FAMILY TIES.....	144
26. Воситов Валижон Абдувахобович ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДА ТУРКИЗМЛАРНИНГ ПАЙДО БЎЛИШ САБАБЛАРИ.....	150
27. Холибекова Омонгул Кенжабоевна ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДАГИ АЛЛЮЗИВ ФРАЗЕОЛОГИК БИРЛИКЛАР ТАЛҚИНИ.....	155
28. Дилбар Холтемировна Ниязова ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИДА ЛИСОНИЙ ШАХС ТИПЛАРИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШГА ХИЗМАТ ҚИЛУВЧИ МАХСУС БИРЛИКЛАР.....	160
29. Шамахмудова Азиза Фуркатовна ҲУРМАТ ТАМОЙИЛЛАРИНИНГ ГЕНДЕР АСПЕКТЛАРИ.....	167
30. Azimov Abdikhamidullo Xolmanovich TO'PLAM IBODATLAR TURLARI VA ULARNING TASNIFI PRINSIPLARI.....	173
31. Boboyev Temur Mahmadmurodovich ROLE OF SHORT HUMOROUS POEMS IN DIFFERENT CULTURAL BACKGROUNDS...	178
32. Ж.О. Каниязова Ш.СЕЙТОВТЫҢ «ЖАМАНШЫҒАНАҚТАҒЫ АҚТУБА» ҲӘМ Ш.ХАЛМЫРЗАЕВТЫҢ “ОЛАБЎЖИ” РОМАНЛАРЫНДА ТУБАЛАЎШЫЛЫҚ ДӘЎИРИНИҢ СУЎРЕТЛЕНИЎИ.....	184
33. Shukurov Foziljon Mahmadvovich TEMURIYLAR DAVRI SHOIRI - BISOTIY SAMARQANDIY G`AZALLARINING POETIKASIDA YANGILIKLAR.....	192

Absamatova Gulhayo Bakhodirovna

Scientific researcher of
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF SIGN LANGUAGE AUTOMATIZATION

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6642151>

ANNOTATION

The article discusses the basic distinguishing features of automatic translation focused on sign languages; general functional requirements for the semantic component of such a system are formulated; the main modern approaches to the construction of automatic translation systems for sign languages are outlined. Many sources of textual information and language communication channels remain inaccessible. The creation of an automatic sign language interpreter capable of bidirectional translation of texts will significantly expand the scope of the use of sign language, including, in particular, features, such relevant tools for today as Internet services and cellular communication systems.

Keywords: multimodal aspect, Sign Language alphabet, trace sign speech, sign language, automatic translation, Russian language, Russian sign language, semantics.

Абсаматова Гулхаё Баходировна

научный сотрудник

Самаркандский государственный институт иностранных языков

ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ АВТОМАТИЗАЦИИ ЖЕСТОВОГО ЯЗЫКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье рассматриваются основные отличительные черты автоматического перевода, ориентированного на жестовые языки; сформулированы общие функциональные требования к смысловой составляющей такой системы; изложены основные современные подходы к построению систем автоматического перевода жестовых языков. Многие источники текстовой информации и каналы языковой коммуникации остаются недоступными. Создание автоматического сурдопереводчика, способного к двунаправленному переводу текстов, позволит значительно расширить сферу использования сурдоперевода, включая, в частности, возможности таких актуальных на сегодняшний день инструментов, как интернет-сервисы и системы сотовой связи.

Ключевые слова: мультимодальный аспект, алфавит языка жестов, трассировка жестовой речи, язык жестов, автоматический перевод, русский язык, русский язык жестов, семантика.

Absamatova Gulhayo Bakhodirovna

Samarqand Davlat Chet Tillar Instituti

IMO-ISHORALAR TARJIMASINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISHNING LINGVISTIK HUSUSIYATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqolada imo-ishora tillariga qaratilgan avtomatik tarjimaning asosiy xususiyatlari muhokama qilinadi; bunday tizimning semantik komponentiga umumiy funktsional talablar shakllantiriladi; imo-ishora tillarini avtomatik tarjima qilish tizimlarini qurishning asosiy zamonaviy yondashuvlari ko'rsatilgan. Ko'pgina matnli ma'lumotlar manbalari va til aloqasi kanallari mavjud emas. Matnlarni ikki tomonlama tarjima qilishga qodir avtomatik surdo tarjimonining yaratilishi surdo-tarjimonlar ko'lamini, xususan, bugungi kunda dolzarb bo'lgan Internet xizmatlari va uyali aloqa tizimlari kabi vositalar imkoniyatlarini sezilarli darajada kengaytiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: multimodal aspekt, imo-ishora tili alifbosi, izli ishorali nutq, imo-ishora tili, avtomatik tarjima, rus tili, rus imo-ishora tili, semantika.

Nowadays there are three main means of communication intended for deaf and hard of hearing people: fingertip alphabet, tracing signed speech, sign language. The first two means, unlike the third, are not independent semiotic systems, but only encode certain components of the Russian-speaking language. The sphere of communication available to native speakers of Sign Language is still much narrower than that of native speakers of Russian-sounding language. The objectives of this article are: to determine the features of sign languages that are essential for the organization of an automatic translation system and predetermine its specificity in comparison with the automatic translation of spoken languages; formulate the basic functional requirements for the semantic component of the system; provide a general picture of the existing automatic translation methods for other sign languages.

From the point of view of modern linguistics, sign languages are independent semiotic systems, classified as natural languages, comparable to them in complexity, but built on the basis of visual-kinetic modalities (changes in the location of hands, their configuration, facial expressions, etc.). Sign languages are in many ways similar to polysynthetic languages [Prozorova, 2006].

These facts alone indicate that this translation is very non-trivial, requires not only knowledge of both semiotic systems and the construction of interlingual correspondences, but also the study of a number of specific problems that the creators of automatic translation systems do not face. Targeting spoken languages. Before considering these problems, we briefly characterize sign languages and the basic principles for their description. Sign languages are predominantly used by deaf and dumb people. There is no consensus on the total number of such languages, some linguists believe that there are a little over a hundred of them, others number hundreds [Wilcox, Morford, 2006]. Modern studies of sign languages, which began in the 60s of the twentieth century. From the works of W. Stokey (Stokoe), are based on the allocation of gesture units, which Stokey called "kerems" ("cherems", "hirems", from the Greek χε. ιρ, χεῖρός - "hand") and subdivided into three classes: 1) configurations of hands (hands), 2) place of production of the sign, 3) nature of movement. Later, a fourth parameter was added - the orientation of the palm of the hand during the production of the sign. The basis for distinguishing these parameters, which modern linguists call "phonemes" [Prozorova, 2006], is the existence of minimal pairs of signs that differ in only one parameter and have different meanings.

Automatic translation, which connects spoken languages with sign languages, involves solving a number of specific problems that do not arise when building automatic translation systems for spoken languages. The main problems can be briefly summarized as follows.

1. Sign language is a multimodal means of communication. The semantic load in it can be carried not only by gestures, but also by non-manual components: gaze, facial expression, position of the head and body. Communication in a spoken language is also multi-modal, but to a much lesser extent, in addition, it can have a single-modal variant (written text). Written sign language notation is not used as a means of communication.

Currently, there is a growing interest in the study of multimodal aspects of communication (in spoken and signed languages). Research is especially active in cognitive science and in the development of multimodal interfaces between humans and computers. However, the existing publicly available automatic translation systems for spoken languages are designed to translate unimodal written texts and therefore do not face a number of specific problems that are associated with automatic translation focused on multimodal communication. Thus, the principles of integration of various input modalities have not yet been developed even for spoken languages [Mittelberg, 2006]. The solution to this problem is complicated by the fact that different modalities are not necessarily synchronized in time. For example, in both spoken and sign language, spontaneous gestures are somewhat ahead of the verbal utterance itself [Ronzhin, Karpov, Lee, 2006, p. 139–141]: when using audio information and video information about the shape of the lips in audiovisual speech recognition systems, it turned out that these modalities are not completely synchronized.

2. So far, there is no unified way to record signs of sign language. Several different notation or transcription systems are used (some of them are discussed in [Mittelberg, 2006]; [Karpov, Kagirow, 2011]), one way or another, using the above four parameters, but defining the domain in different ways. their meanings and symbolic notation. The development of a notation suitable for an automatic translation system is an independent and very difficult problem.

3. Signed languages are less standardized than spoken languages. Insufficient standardization of sign language is evidenced, in particular, by the presence of several dialects of this language. First of all, the St. Petersburg and Moscow dialects of sign language are singled out (according to multimedia dictionaries, the differences between them can reach up to 30-40% of gesture-words [Karpov, Kagirow, 2011]). sign language dialects are used in Belarus, Kazakhstan, Ukraine. Accordingly, the problem arises of choosing those dialects to which the translation will be oriented.

4. Sign language is a mixed semiotic system, within which, in addition to the means included only in sign language, dactyl alphabet and tracing speech can be used. The tactile alphabet is used to introduce and convey the sound of new words (for example, proper names), for which there are no ready-made means of sign language. Calque gestural speech is secondary sign system, it traces the linguistic structure of the sound speaking language. Gestures here are equivalent to words, and their order is the same as in a normal sentence.

This is perhaps the only feature of sign language that facilitates automatic translation: it reduces the significance of the problem of incomplete vocabulary. If, when translating from a spoken language into a sign language, a certain word is not found in any of the available dictionaries, then it can be transmitted using the dactyl alphabet. In automatic translators for spoken languages, such a word is usually simply transferred to the output text in an untranslated form.

5. Signed languages are classified as contact languages that interact with the corresponding spoken languages and are subject to their influence (some examples of such influence in SIGN LANGUAGE are considered by V. I. Kimmelman [Kimmelman, 2009]). When developing a system of automatic sign language translation, the problem arises of identifying the main directions, conditions and results of the influence of SIGN LANGUAGE on SIGN LANGUAGE.

6. As in spoken languages, in sign language, in addition to the signs themselves, gesticulation is also used. However, in a spoken language, gesticulation and verbal speech are realized in their own modality, so they are easily separated from each other. In sign language, a similar distinction is made between lime is impossible: these two components are merged together [Prozorova, 2006a, p. 28]. When automating sign language translation, the problem arises of identifying criteria for delimiting proper SIGN LANGUAGE signs from the accompanying gestures.

7. Unlike spoken language, whose texts are linear, sign language is based on the use of three-dimensional space. A sign of a sign language can theoretically have an infinite number of spatial variations of different meanings. Such, for example, are gestural signs designed to localize conceivable or perceived objects, determine the trajectories of movement, the outlines of objects, etc., varying within the entire area of gesticulation, taking on any of an infinite number of possible values. No other spoken language has an analogous number of verbal designations. The system of sign language notation usually introduces discreteness into the area of gesticulation and, thereby,

impoverishes the language, reducing an infinite number of possible variants of a sign to some finite number. When developing automatic sign language translation (in particular, when choosing a notation system), it is necessary to find some optimal way to solve this problem.

8. Sign languages have certain cognitive features that are significant for the semantic component of the translation system. Let us indicate those of them that seem to be the most important.

At first glance, it might seem that this fact should make different sign languages similar to each other. However, it is not. The similarity does not exceed a certain, not too high, threshold that provides a basic level of mutual understanding: according to [Karpov, Kagirow, 2011], less than 30% of the gestures of different sign languages are the same. Therefore, the creation of a single automatic sign language interpreter that is not focused on a specific sign language is while the task is unrealizable. (International Sign Language is available but not has become widespread.)

The second problem is related to the possibilities of forming metaphors. Metaphors can be used in sign language [Wilcox, Morford, 2006], but this language tool here has specific limitations not found in spoken languages. In particular, the shape of an iconic sign can prevent the formation of metaphors that are quite common for a spoken language. This feature of sign languages is considered in detail in [Meir, 2010] and illustrated by the following example. Many spoken languages use metaphors like “time flies”, “the day has flown by”, etc. However, in Israeli Sign Language it is not possible to use the sign FLY in such expressions. This is explained by the fact that the form of this sign is iconic (waving arms like wings), but in the indicated expressions of sounding languages it is not at all implied that time “flashes its wings”, but it means that flight is a very fast way to move around. - scheniya. The shape of the sign (waving wings) comes into conflict with the aspect of meaning on which the metaphor in spoken language is built (fast movement), which prevents the formation of a similar metaphor in sign language. Thus, spoken language metaphors cannot always be directly translated into sign language. It is natural to assume that the features of the visual kinetic modalities affect other types of figurative meanings in sign languages. This issue requires special consideration when developing automatic translation.

The third problem is caused by the existence of so-called classifier predicates in sign languages. In the iconic sign assigned to this class, the trajectory of the movement of the hand corresponds to the trajectory of the object-participant of the described situation, and the shape of the hand reflects some significant properties of this object, while the same shape of the hand can serve to designate a whole class of objects with similar external features [Prozorova, 2006]. The classifier predicates capable of representing a three-dimensional situation most clearly reflect the possibility of infinite variation of the sign of a sign language. This complicates the application of traditional methods of computational linguistics in the construction of an automatic translation system. Indeed, the experience of developing systems for translating texts from English-sounding language into ASL shows that in order to model such predicates, it is necessary to use semantic analysis, knowledge about the world, about spatial relations, means reasoning [Huenerfauth, 2003; 2004]. The problem is exacerbated by the fact that the frequency of use of classifier predicates is quite high: approximately one such predicate occurs per minute in Amslen speech [Huenerfauth, 2004].

The development of a sign language-oriented automatic translation system should be based on one degree or another.

The experience of developing automatic translation systems for sign languages is about two decades. There are two main approaches: rule-based translation and data-based translation. In systems of the first type, translation rules are built manually based on knowledge of both languages, in systems of the second type, rules are derived automatically based on computer analysis of language data, which does not rely on any prior knowledge about the structure of the languages under consideration. An example of a second type of system is statistical automatic translation.

One of the systems of the first type was proposed in [Huenerfauth, 2004]. The author focuses on the possibility of translating classifier predicates. He compares the existing systems of the first type (rule-based), translating English-speaking texts into Amslen, in terms of their ability to work with different types of texts [Huenerfauth, 2003].

1. Direct translation: word by word translation without parsing.

2. Transfer. The input text is analyzed at the level of syntax (or semantics), after which a set of translation rules (“transfer”) generates the corresponding syntactic (or semantic) structure of the output language. At the next stage, the generating component of the system converts this structure into the text of the target language.

3. Interlingua. In this case, the analysis of the input text goes even deeper: a semantic representation (“interlingua”) is built in a special artificial language that does not depend on the input and output languages. Based on this representation, the generating component of the system generates the text of the output language in stages.

These three types of systems can be depicted as a pyramid [Huenerfauth, 2003]. The higher the pyramid reaches the analysis of the language, the more complex and subtle this analysis is, the more dramatically increases the amount of work that must be done by the creators of the system. For direct translation, only a bilingual dictionary is required, when using transfer, the rules of syntactic (semantic) analysis and the actual transfer rules are added, for interlingua, a language for describing deep semantics and, possibly, a knowledge base specific to the subject area under consideration.

Direct translation gives acceptable results when the word order in the English text and in the Amslen is the same. The transfer will make it possible to cope with most of the sentences of the Amslen, which do not require a complex analysis of the three-dimensional gestural space. Classifier predicates require a third type approach (interlingua). Thus, each of the methods is suitable for its own type of texts, so [Huenerfauth, 2004] proposes to combine all these methods in one system capable of choosing the trajectory of text translation depending on its type.

As stated in [Dreuw et al., 2008], data-based automatic translation is now quite intensively used. Such systems exist, for example, for German, Dutch, Irish, Chinese Sign Languages.

The question of what results the use of different principles for organizing automatic translation for Sign Language yields remains to be explored.

Literature

1. Dreuw P., Stein D., Deselaers T., Rybach D., Zahedi M., Bungeroth J., Ney H. Spoken Language Processing Techniques for Sign Language Recognition and Translation // *Technology and Disability*. Vol. 20, N. 2. 2008. P. 121–133.
2. Huenerfauth M. A Multi-Path Architecture for Machine Translation of English Text into American Sign Language Animation // *Proceedings of the Student Workshop at the Human Language Technology conference / North American chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics annual meeting (HLT-NAACL 2004)*, Boston, MA, USA. 2004. P. 25–30.
3. Huenerfauth M. A Survey and Critique of American Sign Language Natural Language Generation and Machine Translation Systems. Technical Report MS-CIS-03- 32, Computer and Information Science, University of Pennsylvania. 2003.
4. Mittelberg I. Methodology for multimodality: one way of working with speech and gesture data // *Methods in cognitive linguistics*. Amsterdam; Philadelphia, 2006. P. 225–248.
5. Wilcox S., Morford J. P. Empirical methods in signed language research // *Methods in cognitive linguistics*. Amsterdam; Philadelphia, 2006. P. 171–200.
6. Кибрик А.А., Прозорова Е.В. Референциальный выбор в русском жестовом языке // *Компьютерная лингвистика и интеллектуальные технологии: Труды международной конференции «Диалог 2007» (Бекасово, 30 мая – 3 июня 2007 г.)*. М., 2007. С. 220–230.
7. Киммельман В.И. Базовый порядок слов в русском жестовом языке: Дипломная работа. М., 2010.
8. Киммельман В.И. Нерегулярные отрицания в русском жестовом языке // *Структуры и интерпретации: Работы молодых исследователей по теоретической и прикладной лингвистике*. М., 2007. С. 89–103.
9. Королькова О.О. Сопоставление морфологии русского звучащего и русского жестового языка // *Приложение к журналу «В мире научных открытий»*. Красноярск, 2011. Вып. 1:

Материалы IV Всероссийской научно-практической конференции с междунар. участием «Научное творчество XXI века» (апрель 2011 г.). С. 182–183.

10. Прозорова Е.В. Маркеры локальной структуры дискурса в русском жестовом языке: Автореф. дис. ... канд. филол. наук. М., 2009.
11. Прозорова Е.В. Референциальные характеристики именных групп в русском (русском) жестовом языке. Дипломная работа. М., 2006а.
12. Прозорова Е.В. Является ли российский жестовый язык полисинтетическим?//Третья конференция по типологии и грамматике: Материалы. СПб, 2006б. С. 128–132.

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 5, НОМЕР 3

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 5, ISSUE 3

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000